

Dora Immune Harpin Protein Products

Dora Agri is the professional supplier and exporter of Harpin Protein based products (plant elicitor of disease resistance) for sale with five years of export experience. Our primary market is Central & South America, and Western Europe cooperated with powerful distributors.

Dora Immune is our exclusive Harpin Protein based plant health regulators. This product contains Harpin and other natural organic matters. Usually, it acted as a plant health promoter activates a plant's immune system, which triggers growth and defence genes.

When Dora Immune contacts with plants' receptors on their seeds, roots, and leaves, it will trigger an early warning system — "Systemic Acquired Resistance," leading to increased plant yields and health.

Target Crops: Economic crops such as cannabis, tobacco, Asparagus, avocado, mango, grape, citrus, blueberry, kiwi, apple, grape, plum, cherry, blueberry, avocado, nectarine etc.

If you have the need to buy harpin protein product, please feel free to email us at dora@doraagri.com and WhatsApp +86 18018160216.

Mechanism of Harpin Protein

As the diagram shows, Dora Immune works by stimulating the plant to grow under the general effects of stress and one of those stresses is fungal attack. Harpin itself does not directly affect the pathogens, nor does it enter the plant, rather it binds to receptors on the plant leaf and thereby triggers physiological processes within the plant.

Features of Harpin Protein

- Increases plant yield and quality
- Improves nutrients uptake ability
- Help crop defend against plant diseases
- Extend fruits shelf-life 5-7 days
- Increase fruit sugars 10%-25%
- Increase calcium uptake by > 20%

Specification of Harpin Protein

Product Name	Dora Immune	Ingredients	Harpin Protein
Appearance	Brown Liquid	pH	6.0-7.0
Density	1.14g/ml	Shelf Life	2 years

Applications of Harpin Protein

1. Induce Crops to Prevent Diseases

Dora Immune is an environmentally-friendly **elicitor** of disease resistance. It can induce 70 kinds of disease resistance, the prevention rate & control effect of the disease is from 40%-80%.

2. Increase Plant Immunity

Stimulate crop strong repairing ability to the diseases caused by many types of adverse environmental damage. Especially for post-disaster recovery of crops, quickly promote crops' regeneration. Restore growth and development capacity. Greatly reduce the losses caused by disasters.

3. Stimulate Plant Growth

Promote plant growth and development, self-repair, nutrient absorption and transportation, and achieve high quality and high yield, significantly increase crops yield and quality can increase crop yield by 10-55%.

How to use Harpin Protein

1. Foliar Application

125 ml Dora Immune per 100 L water. In general, apply 3-5 times during the germination period, seedling stage, flowering period and the last week before maturing.

2. Seed Soaking

Soak your seeds or tubers in a Dora Immune concentrated solution which diluted 1000 times. It is allowed to dissolve it into the solution for at least 30 minutes, shake, then soak your seeds or tubers for 10 minutes before sowing.

3. Mixture

1. Dora Immune can be mixed with other products(PH 6~7), and should be used within 2-6 hours after being formulated.
2. Use within 1 hour once mixed with products containing heavy metal ions, because the heavy metal ions can adsorb the harpin protein, thus impact it contacting with plant receptors.

Field Trial of Harpin Protein

1. Use on Tomato

2. Use on Cucumber

3. Use on Melon

4. Use on Coffee

Feedback

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